

Table 1. Symptoms^a and plant height reduction at 30 and 60 d after infection in 10 rice varieties infected with RSV 7 d after soaking, Sep 1984, IRRI.

Variety	30 d after infection		60 d after infection	
	Symptoms	Height reduction (%)	Symptoms	Height reduction (%)
Sitopas	R ⁺⁺⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	24	Tw, V	7
Ptb 18	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	29	R ⁺ , V ⁺⁺	17
Tetep	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	29	R ⁺⁺ , V ⁺	22
Lemo	R ⁺ , Tw	57	R ⁺⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	36
Ptb 21	R ⁺ , Tw	59	V ⁺⁺	20
Utri Rajapan	R ⁺	52	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	21
Khao Mali	Tw	43	V ⁺⁺	21
Khao-Tah-Haeng	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	45	R ⁺⁺ , V ⁺	43
Kirikara	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	68	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺⁺	34
TN1	R ⁺ , V ⁺	56	R ⁺⁺ , Tw, V ⁺⁺	25

^aR = ragged leaves, Tw = twisted leaves, V = vein swelling. +, ++, +++ = degree of severity from low to high.

Table 2. Yield reduction in 10 rice varieties infected with RSV at different days after soaking, IRRI, Sep 1984.

Variety	Yield reduction (%)				
	7 DAS	15 DAS	30 DAS	45 DAS	60 DAS
Sitopas	41	55	28	35	3
Ptb 18 ^a	38	65	28	21	-
Tetep	22	58	30	46	5
Lemo	57	-	33	-28	-21
Ptb 21	99	53	-10	-3	-22
Utri Rajapan	100	59	35	5	-39
Khao Mali	80	79	32	47	-16
Khao-Tah-Haeng	100	100	15	28	52
Kirikara	77	96	34	52	20
TN1	84	90	78	65	2

^a Percentage yield reduction was calculated based on the yield of plants inoculated at 60 DAS.

Tetep. The symptoms in plants infected at 30 DAS were milder and those in plants infected at 45 DAS were not clear in any varieties except Kirikara and TN1.

In the first trial, yield reduction was high in plants of almost all varieties infected at 7 or 15 DAS (Table 2). Sitopas, Ptb 18, Tetep, and Lemo have significantly less yield reduction than other varieties infected at the seedling stages. In the second trial, flowering was delayed and yield reduction was less than in the first trial in all varieties. Yield reduction in many varieties inoculated at 30 DAS was higher than in plants inoculated at 7 or 15 DAS. Sitopas, Ptb 18, Lemo, and Ptb 21 had significantly lower yield reduction.

Sitopas, Ptb 18, Lemo, and Tetep developed milder symptoms and sustained less damage when infected with RSV at seedling stage. Their tolerance for RSV was due to their high ability to recover after severe infection at an early stage. □

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Incidence of rice kernel smut (KSm) in Pakistan

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Sixteen rice varieties were evaluated at Gujranwala and Sheikhpura district research farms against KSm by the partial vacuum method using the chlamydospores of *Tilletia barclayana*. Sporidial cultures were prepared on potato dextrose agar for inoculation of 20 panicles of each variety at anthesis. Percentages of infected panicles were recorded at maturity.

Varieties showed differential reaction at both locations. Disease incidence ranged from 5.25 to 95.25% at Sheikhpura and 6.25 to 97.25% at Gujranwala. C622 developed the lowest

Reaction of rice varieties to *Tilletia barclayana*. Islamabad, Pakistan.

Variety	Disease incidence (%)		Reaction
	Sheikhpura	Gujranwala	
Bara, Basmati Pak, Dokri Basmati, Jhona 349, Kangni, Melha 364, Motia, Mushakan, Palman, Ratria, Red rice, Sathra 278	>50	>50	Susceptible
Basmati 370, Sada gulab C622, IR579	>10 <10	>10 <10	Intermediate Resistant

infection, followed by IR579 and Basmati 370 (see table).

None of the varieties appeared to be immune. □

Reaction of selected varieties to tungro (RTV) and green leafhopper (GLH)

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Seven-day-old seedlings of ASD7, ARC11554, Gam Pai 30-12-15, Kataribhog, TKM6, TN1, and Utri Rajapan were individually exposed to one or five RTV-viruliferous adult